

Influence of social media on body image dissatisfaction among adolescents and young adults

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Abstract

Body image dissatisfaction is a growing concern among adolescents and young adults, often intensified by the pervasive influence of social media. This study explores how platforms often contribute to negative self-perception by promoting unrealistic beauty standards, encouraging peer comparison, and increasing admiration for social media influencers. We conducted as a cross-sectional descriptive study in Thiruvalla Taluk, data were collected from 500 students across schools and colleges using structured questionnaires. The findings revealed that prolonged screen time, use of photo-enhancement tools, and exposure to idealized images significantly correlate with body image dissatisfaction. Female participants showed greater dissatisfaction than males, and young adults were more affected than adolescents. These results emphasize the urgent need for digital literacy, psychological support, and awareness programs that promote body positivity and challenge unrealistic social norms perpetuated online.

Keywords: Body Image Dissatisfaction; Social Media Influence; Adolescents; Young Adults

1. Introduction

Body image is the term used to describe a person's emotional attitudes, perceptions, and beliefs about their own body. These ideas can have a significant negative impact on an individual's nutritional status and ultimately affect their mental and physical health as adults and adolescents ⁽¹⁾. A number of things, including friends, family, the media, and society as a whole, can contribute to body image dissatisfaction. The "thin-ideal" for female beauty and the "athletic image" for males appear to be the main sources of pressure from the media and society. Although everyone is subject to this pressure, teenagers are more susceptible to it. ⁽²⁾ The development of body image dissatisfaction has been linked to the significant impact of negative family communication around body image, including taunting, criticism, and encouragement to diet. ⁽³⁾ Most societies have nearly always created ideals of beauty and attractiveness, which has often been extremely difficult to achieve. However, it has been suggested that the media does not drive the development of body dissatisfaction but reminds individuals of their already – existent body dissatisfaction. ⁽⁷⁾

Social media has become a powerful cultural force that continuously shapes societal norms and personal ideals, particularly concerning body image. Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and Snapchat routinely showcase idealized representations of beauty—slim, flawless bodies in women and muscular, athletic physiques in men—that can distort viewers' perceptions of their own appearance ⁽¹¹⁾. These curated and often edited visuals contribute to a heightened awareness of physical flaws and reinforce unattainable beauty standards, making individuals—especially adolescents and young adults—vulnerable to body image dissatisfaction.

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Increased screen time and appearance-based interactions have been strongly associated with higher levels of anxiety, poor self-image, and social comparison⁽³⁾. As social media continues to shape beauty standards, its psychological impact on youth calls for critical attention and digital awareness.

2. Study methodology

2.1. Study design

This study was designed as a Cross-Sectional Descriptive Study, which was carried out in 2 Schools and 3 Colleges, Thiruvalla taluk, Kerala for a time-period of 6 months. The sample size was determined to be 500 participants. The study was conducted after receiving approval from the Institutional Review Board of Nazareth College of Pharmacy, Othara, Thiruvalla.

For this study, a set of pre-determined criteria was developed:

2.2. Inclusion criteria

Population of age between 13-25.

2.3. Exclusion criteria

- Pediatrics below age 12.
- Differently abled student population.
- Pregnant and breastfeeding women.

2.3.1. Sources Of Data

The data required for the study was collected from the schools and colleges.

2.4. Data Collection Technique

A pilot study was conducted at Nazareth college of Pharmacy using a pre-designed questionnaire to assess the feasibility of the proposed study. Participants were enrolled in the study according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The data was collected through Community visits to the Schools and Colleges of Thiruvalla Taluk. Participants were asked to fill out a prepared questionnaire to determine the prevalence of body image dissatisfaction and the influence of life style factors like BMI, Diet and Physical activity. Individuals were provided with a brief introduction regarding the study and confidentiality of data was explained to them. The pre-designed questionnaire forms were provided to the school students and google forms to the rest and they were collected back. A short verbal awareness were given

2.5. Data Collection Tools

- Pre-Designed Questionnaire
- Google forms
- Informed Consent form

Statistical Analysis: The data collected were entered in the MS excel 2021 version and results were analyzed as tabular form and percentage.

3. Results

3.1. Influence of social media on participants

3.1.1. Data to estimate level of envy towards others appearance on social media.

Figure 1 Data on levels of envy towards others appearance on social media

The above graph shows that among the 500 study participants, 9.80% always felt jealous about others appearance on social media, 39.00% only felt it sometimes, and 51.20% never had envy of others appearance on social media.

3.1.2. Data on influence of social media on body image perception

Figure 2 Data on influence of social media on body image perception

The aforementioned graph of 500 study participants, of which 6.80% always have influence of social media on body perception, 41.20% never have and 19.80% rarely have, and 32.20% sometimes have an influence.

3.1.3. Data on screen time in social media

Figure 3 Data on screen time in social media

The above graph shows that of the 500 study participants ,26.00% spends less than an hour on social media ,69.40% spends more than 2 hours on social media and 4.60% do not use any social media.

3.1.4. Data on admiring the appearance of social idols/influencers

Figure 4 Data on admiring the appearance of social idols/influencers

The aforementioned pie chart signifies that 56.00% of the 500 study participants admires the appearance of models/social media influencers,17.40% are influenced by appearance of actor/actress ,16.20% of them admire the physical appearance of their relatives and friends and about 10.40% admire no one.

3.1.5. Data on use of photo enhancement techniques

Figure 5 Data on use of photo enhancement techniques

The above graph indicates that among 500 study participants 15.40% frequently use photo filters while taking photos of themselves, 30.20% never use filters and about 54.40% sometimes uses filters.

4. Discussion

Dissatisfaction with one's body image is said to arise from a perceived difference between one's intended ideal state of the body and one's actual physical appearance. The term "body image" refers to an individual's emotional attitudes, perceptions, and beliefs regarding their own physical appearance with an influence of various factors such as friends, family, the media, and society across the world.

Our study aims to determine the prevalence of body image dissatisfaction among age groups of adolescents and young adults. A study population of 500 students from schools and colleges were chosen as participants. The study was a cross-sectional study. The data of the patients were collected using structured questionnaires and Google Forms.

Our findings highlight the substantial influence of social media on body image perception among adolescents and young adults. The prevalence of body image dissatisfaction was found out among the 500 study participants 73.00% (365) study participants have body image dissatisfaction and the remaining 27.00% (135) participants were satisfied with their body image.

4.1. Social media pressures

In the research study conducted by Alruwayshid MS *et al*,⁽⁴⁾ among 204 college students in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The results shows around 47.1% of participants spend more than 4 hours in social media and their dissatisfaction levels among the students are low, This is contrasted in our study showing that among the study participants 69.4% use social media for more than 2 hours, while 26% use social media for less than 1 hour and 4.6% does not use any kinds of social media. Social media use shows a direct link with BID in our study.

From our study to rule out envy towards others it was found that 48.8% felt jealous and 51.2% did not feel jealous and this shows that envy of others appearance on social media had no link with BID. So these findings were in contrast with the study conducted by Virk and Nagar⁽⁵⁾ conducted a study on 60 female students in different colleges in Delhi, the study indicates that young urban Indian women experience dissatisfaction and reduced self when exposed to western thin ideal images to the same extent. Further more the findings suggests that media images of duration more than a minute can lead to increased envy to the social media idols.

Ho *et al*,⁽⁶⁾ conducted a study on 1059 adolescents in Singapore, the study indicates that SNSs and social comparison public figures was significantly associated with BID. This is contrasted to our study only 44% were influenced by the appearance social idols/influencers and 56% were not.

With the recent scenario in our study, the use of filters while clicking pictures has been increased by 69.8% in order to modify their appearance, which develops dissatisfaction.

5. Conclusion

The study revealed a strong association between prolonged social media use and body image dissatisfaction among adolescents and young adults. Increased screen time, admiration of social media influencers, and frequent use of photo filters were key contributors to negative body perception. These findings highlight the growing impact of digital platforms in shaping unrealistic beauty standards, emphasizing the need for media literacy and body-positive awareness among youth.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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